

Conjoint analysis-based product identity of combustion and electric car design properties

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Actually, the number of new electric vehicle (EV) models has multiplied, thus generating a trend in the market. In the trend analyses consulted on the attitudes of users in relation to EVs, particularly with electric cars, in none does the aesthetic or design factor appear as a purchase motivation. This study proposes a methodology where through conjoint analysis carried out, identification is made of which formal aesthetic properties of the front of a car are associated with electric cars, the main characteristics being the lack of a grille, headlight form type “double arc”, front form type “smile”, and a bonnet form type “arc”. Furthermore, several ANOVAs are performed to study the relationship between formal aesthetic properties and socio-demographic characteristics.

Keywords: aesthetics; user participation; automotive design; product design

Introduction

According to data published in the International Energy Agency (IEA) report in 2022, sales of electric vehicles (EV) worldwide doubled in 2021 compared to the previous year, and accounted for almost 10% of global EV sales. Much of the boost in EV sales comes from policies supporting this product, such as subsidies and purchase incentives (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2022).

The increase in new EV models has multiplied fivefold in the last 5 years, with an availability of more than 500 models in 2022 and approximately 16.5 million EVs sold worldwide (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2022). This increase is rendering the market more competitive and new markets are emerging with more affordable models and better features (BloombergNEF (BNEF), 2023). The highest percentage of EVs sold today is in 2- and 3-wheeled vehicles (49%) and in buses (38%). As for cars, EVs represent 14% of total sales of this type of vehicle (BloombergNEF (BNEF), 2023).

In relation to EV users, the study carried out by the electric mobility services company Electromaps on the Spanish public concludes that 97% of Spanish EV owners would buy an EV again (Rodríguez, 2023). The main reasons given for purchasing such a vehicle include fuel savings (72.9%), respect for the environment (70.1%), and innovation (35.5%). On the other hand, based on the data provided by the Cetelem Observatory in 2023, the main factors that discourage the Spanish public from buying an EV are the high price (66%), insufficient autonomy (57%), and the lack of infrastructure to charge the batteries (40%) in addition to the charging time (39%) (Observatorio Cetelem, 2023). Kantar, the world's leading data, insights and consulting company, establishes that consumers are optimistic about the future of the EV market and put the possible price reduction, the development of infrastructure, and the development of advanced functions such as autonomous driving as the main motivating factors for purchasing EVs in the future (Kantar, 2023).

Product identity

In the trend analyses consulted on user attitudes in relation to EVs, in particular with electric cars, in none does the aesthetic or design factor appear as a purchase motivation, probably since there is no specific style that defines electric cars (Electric Vehicle Council, 2022). It is therefore of interest to analyse those formal aesthetic attributes that can enhance the identity of EVs since they currently share styling with conventional vehicles.

The development of electric cars was launched from the existing platform design of combustion vehicles, and hence the current style of EVs is similar to that of traditional vehicles. Although the layout and internal configurations differ in electric cars from other cars because the location of the engines and charging make new configurations possible, the exterior design remains an inheritance from combustion vehicles.

In most cases, the styling of EVs is marked by the use of space and aerodynamics. In the case of EVs, there are studies that analyse how to take advantage of this new layout to generate new functional styling whose priority is to reduce the aerodynamic coefficient of the vehicle (Li & Zhu, 2019).

Cagan and Vogel, in their book “Creating Breakthrough products”, establish seven areas of value for a new product to be considered a breakthrough product: emotion, aesthetics, identity, ergonomics, impact, technology, and quality (Cagan & Vogel, 2002). The authors understand aesthetics as the area that deals with the sensory perceptions produced by the product, not only visually, but also including those perceptions of all the other senses. On the other hand, identity is an important area in the development of EV styling, since identity gives the product an individual, unique character, with a current style adapted to the environment and circumstances of use. Cagan and Vogel establish that personality is based on the product's ability to differentiate itself from the competition and the connection of the product with the rest of the company's products. For those companies whose product portfolio is mainly traditional vehicles, this definition of identity makes it more difficult for them to create their own EV identity. Hence Tesla can be considered a company with a commitment to innovation in electric car styling since its own brand identity is EVs (Ferro, Costabile, & Tedeschi, 2020). When developing new products,

the relationship of the new product's identity to the rest of the products in the company's portfolio presents a critical aspect for consideration (Han, Liu, & Zhang, 2009). In these cases, the company has two options: maintain the brand identity in its new product or allow the identity of the new product to predominate over the identity of the company (Zhu, Zhang, Qin, & Li, 2022). Mahdi (2020) establishes that the strategy based on product identity involves the difficulty of having to provide change under integration that is, applying heterogeneity within homogeneity (Mahdi, 2020).

In relation to users, it is important to analyse their perception of EVs, since being a new product it must seek to be recognisable by the rest of the users, thus marking a difference at a perceptual level with respect to traditional vehicles. (Bennett & Vijaygopal, 2018). Schuitema et al. (2013) found that EV owners undergo emotions of pleasure and pride when owning an electric car, and concluded that those people who have a pro-environmental self-identity are more likely to acquire an EV that enhances that self-identity and transmits it to others. (Schuitema, Anable, Skippon, & Kinnear, 2013). The authors establish that current perceptions of EV attributes are weakly associated with this pro-environmental identity. From the point of view of the user of an electric car, it is important that they be able to communicate to other people that they are the owner of this type of vehicle since it helps strengthen their self-image (Bennett & Vijaygopal, 2018). A product with an identity supports emotion and reinforces “the consumer's fantasy in owning and using the product” (Cagan & Vogel, 2002).

That is why it is considered of interest to analyse which attributes best define an electric car to help provide future electric cars with their own identity through aesthetics and styling, thereby making them distinguishable in the market and in their surroundings.

1. Background

In order to address the study of the attributes and properties that define a product and its relationship with the user, market research techniques and product design and development techniques are employed.

Within market research techniques, one of the most widely used is that of conjoint analysis (CA), which enables the research team to analyse which attributes and which attribute levels of the product are the most important or attractive and which are the most irrelevant or least attractive. Conjoint analysis in the automotive sector has largely been employed to analyse purchase intention attributes, although it can also be used to obtain relevant information on aesthetic and functional attributes. (Suzianti, Apriliandary, & Priscandy, 2016; Wu, Liao, & Chatwuthikrai, 2014).

An example of the application of conjoint analysis in vehicle market research is given by that proposed by Darzianazizi and Ghasemi (2013), in which the most important criteria for brand positioning are analysed. In this case, we work with 4 attributes with 3 levels: company's marketing (reputation, price, and promotion), appearance (safety, design, and convenience), technical features (quality, consumption, and innovation) and services of the company (after-sales service, availability of spare parts, and warranty) (Darzianazizi & Ghasemi, 2013).

Conjoint analysis can also be used to analyse what factors affect a car purchasing decision. Kabadayi, Alan & Özkan (2013) propose analysing attributes such as fuel type, price, security, fuel consumption level, and the automobile style (Kabadayi, Alan, & Özkan, 2013). In marketing, it is common to use conjoint analysis to analyse the behaviour of users when making a decision to purchase a car (Jamali Hondori, Javanshir, & Rabani, 2013; Numon, Ho, Ho, & Shin, 2019).

Regarding EV, Kowalska et al. (2022), analyse purchasing preferences for electric cars through conjoint analysis, for which they propose 11 attributes (price, brand, range, access to service, access to charging stations, car segment, functional values, safety, type of fuel, reuse of batteries, and impact of weather batteries). From this study, it was concluded that the most valued attributes when choosing an electric vehicle are safety, followed by price and range (Kowalska-Pyzalska, Michalski, Kott, Skowrońska-Szmer, & Kott, 2022).

Moons and De Pelsmacker (2014) use conjoint analysis to analyse the experience evoked in EV (Moons & De Pelsmacker, 2014). Rudolph (2016) analyses which type of incentives are preferred

by users in the purchase of EVs, such as direct subsidies, a separate CO_2 tax, free parking, increase of available charging infrastructure, and an increase of fuel costs by tax elevation (Rudolph, 2016).

Regarding the formal aesthetic aspects of the vehicle, Suzianti et al. (2016) use conjoint analysis to analyse the external aesthetic attributes of the vehicle in users' decision-making, and refer to the users' affective perception. Certain studies focus their attention on a specific element of the vehicle. Through conjoint analysis, Muslim et al. (2019) propose analysing the attributes that define an electric car's indicator panel and the conventional car's indicator panel (Muslim, Moch, Lestari, Shabrina, & Ramardhiani, 2019).

The electric car study proposed by Xi et al. (2017) establish that, in order to evoke a “hi-tech” appearance in an EV, the attributes “headlight”, “front face shape”, and “front grille” are the most important. Going into detail, the “long and thin shape” of the headlights and the “X type” shape for the front shape constitute the most predominant attributes (Xi, Cheng, Wu, Ye, & Xiao, 2017). The conclusions of these reference studies are highly useful in establishing the design attributes to be taken into account in the present study.

All studies presented herein include an analysis of demographic characteristics through surveys that help to better understand user preferences and obtain detailed data based on said characteristics.

1.2 Hypotheses and objectives

This research is based on the following hypotheses:

- H1: There are attributes and formal aesthetic attribute levels that are more influential than others in the identification of a car as either electric or combustion.
- H2: Currently it is difficult to identify a car as either electric or combustion through visual perception.
- H3: There are social and/or demographic variables that influence the perception of a car as either electric or combustion.

The objectives proposed in this research are:

- O1: Define a series of attributes and attribute levels relevant to establishing the identity of an electric car and obtain a sample space for study.
- O2: Apply conjoint analysis to obtain relevant information regarding which attributes and levels contribute the most to the identity of an electric vehicle and identify the attributes and levels that fail to contribute towards such identification.
- O3: Analyse the degree of success and failure in the classification of vehicles as either electric or combustion.
- O4: Analyse whether there are differences in the results based on social and demographic characteristics, such as sex, age, purchase intention, and pro-environmental awareness.

Objectives O1 and O2 are set to analyse Hypothesis H1, O3 is set to analyse H2, and O4 is set to analyse H3.

The first section of this work includes an introduction to the automobile and EV sector, followed by the EV-focused product identity and a background that serves as a reference for the study, and ends with the proposal of hypotheses and objectives. The second section establishes the methodological proposal applied to achieve the objectives. The third section presents the results obtained in the experimental application of the proposed methodology. Lastly, Section 4 draws the conclusions of the research carried out.

2. Materials and methods

In order to achieve the objectives defined in 1.3, a methodology divided into four phases is established (Figure 1). In the first phase, a background analysis (1.2) is carried out to define the method and techniques with which to achieve the objectives. In the second phase, a questionnaire is carried out to obtain information from the user. The next phase involves the application of the conjoint analysis method to analyse user preferences for electric cars. Lastly, a visual test is carried out to analyse the users' ability to recognise an electric car.

Figure 1. Proposed methodology

2.1 Questionnaire survey

Subsequent to the background analysis (1.2), it was considered necessary to conduct a questionnaire for users to obtain socio-demographic information since this type of questionnaire was present in all the studies analysed. Furthermore, questions are included that help establish the relationship between users and the object of study, in this case, the electric car. The studies under analysis were used as the basis for the definition of the questions to be included in the questionnaire, together with several of our own proposals focused on the object of study. This questionnaire is a closed multiple-choice survey in which seven variables have been established: P1, Sex; P2, Age; P3, Driving licence; P4, Ecological choice; P5, Purchase preference for a 100% electric car; P6, Desire to purchase a 100% electric car; P7, Ability to differentiate a 100% electric car. Variables P1 to P3 have the objective of categorising the user (socio-demographic variables) and variables P4 to P7 have the objective of analysing the relationship between the user and the electric car. In the experiment, the first step informs the respondents regarding the objective and confidentiality of the experiments and then begins carrying out the anonymous questionnaire. The questionnaire is helpful in achieving Objective 4 of the study (O4).

2.2 Conjoint Analysis

The next phase in the proposed methodology is to carry out a conjoint analysis to achieve Objective 1 (O1) and Objective 2 (O2). Conjoint analysis has been chosen since it is one of the most widely employed analysis techniques to understand user preferences, as defined in the background analysis (1.2). Conjoint analysis is applied in order to ascertain the aesthetic-formal attributes that best define an electric car while simultaneously ascertaining the attributes that best define a combustion car.

Conjoint analysis is a multi-attribute technique focused on analysing user choices to explain the way in which they establish their system of preferences for a product. A user's preference for a product is due to the conjoint effect of attributes defined by their attribute levels that constitute the product (Wilkie & Pessemier, 1973). Hence the objective of the conjoint analysis is to obtain the quantitative value, called utility, associated with each attribute level of the product analysed.

In order to explain a user's preferences for a product, the conjoint analysis is based on the decomposition strategy. This strategy, at a practical level, means that users must order or rate a series of products, from which is attained a quantitative value of the individual importance of each attribute and the usefulness associated with each attribute level (Ferreira, 2011).

Based on previous studies, eight stages are defined for the application of conjoint analysis of this study (Churchill & Iacobucci, 2002; Ferreira, 2011; Green & Srinivasan, 1978; Numon et al., 2019): 1. Definition of the objective; 2. Selection of attributes and the attribute levels; 3. Selection of the conjoint methodology; 4. Specification of the combinations of characteristics and application of an orthogonal factorial design; 5. Selection of questionnaire method; 6. Data collection; 7. Estimation of the importance of attributes and the utilities of attribute levels; 8. Evaluation of the validity.

2.2.1 Definition of the objective

The objective of applying conjoint analysis is to analyse which formal aesthetic attributes and attribute levels define an electric vehicle as opposed to a combustion vehicle based on the visual

perception of the users. For the study of a car, the front of a vehicle has been chosen for analysis since it is a complex three-dimensional product whereby each view has a differing series of attributes and the front constitutes the most characteristic and differentiating view between types of vehicles and brands.

2.2.2 Selection of attributes and attribute levels

The attributes are the characteristics into which the front of a car can be broken down, and the levels are the various alternatives that can exist within each attribute. The studies described in the background analysis (1.2) and our own proposals after carrying out a market analysis of existing vehicles together provided the basis for the selection of the attributes. The attributes and their levels under study are: headlight form (arc, double arc, fine, polygonal, rounded); headlight separation (yes, no); grille form (long thin, organic, banner, polygonal, visual, no grille); front form (big mouth, integrated, smile, type U, type X); bonnet form (arc, straight, straight arc); and the bonnet nerve (line, double line, no nerve). The selected attributes are not correlated with each other, and the levels are consistent across the board to ensure that no unrealistic combinations are obtained.

To present the selected attributes and their levels, the morphological chart technique has been chosen, which enables the levels of the attributes to be defined graphically, which is ideal for establishing formal aesthetic attributes. (Suzianti et al., 2016). In Figure 2, in addition to including a representative image of the attribute level, a linguistic term and an identifier have been defined for each level.

Attribute	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6
Headlight form	Arc 					
Headlight separation	Yes 					
Grille form	Long thin 					
Front form	Big mouth 					
Bonnet form	Arc 					
Bonnet nerve	Line 					

Figure 2. Morphological chart of attributes and levels

2.2.3 Selection of the conjoint methodology

There are variants within the conjoint analysis, and therefore, before continuing, a conjoint methodology must be chosen. In this case study, traditional conjoint analysis (full-profile conjoint analysis) has been employed since this type of analysis best adapts to the objectives of the study and provides the most information. In conjoint analysis, a profile is understood as the specific combination of attribute levels that defines a product.

On a practical level, full-profile conjoint analysis is based on requesting users to order a set of profiles based on their preferences. They may also be asked to individually rate each profile shown. In this case study, the profiles are the different combinations of levels of the attributes defined in Figure 2, giving rise to multiple car fronts.

2.2.4 Specification of the combinations of characteristics and application of an orthogonal factorial design

Given the attributes and levels defined in the morphological chart (Figure 2), the number of possible combinations or profiles to obtain would number 2,700 ($5 \times 2 \times 6 \times 5 \times 3 \times 3$). When the full-

profile conjoint analysis approach is applied, a high number of combinations or profiles tends to be obtained, and hence a reduction is necessary, since it would be unfeasible for users to evaluate so many profiles.

Reducing the number of profiles is common in the full-profile conjoint analysis approach, for which a fractional factorial design is used through the use of orthogonal matrices. With the application of this technique, it is possible to obtain a representative and adequate fraction of all the possible combinations of attribute levels. (Jiao, Xu, & Helander, 2007; Numon et al., 2019). To carry out the fractional factorial design, the IBM SPSS Statistics v.26.0 software is applied via the “Orthogonal Design” function. This application has resulted in 49 profiles.

2.2.5 Selection of questionnaire method

The 49 resulting profiles are represented graphically, these being the fronts of real cars. Of these 49 fronts, it has been decided to have an almost equal representation of electric cars (n=24) and combustion cars (n=25).

When using photographic representations of the fronts of real cars, these have been treated to eliminate attributes that are not the object of study and that can distort the data of the experiment, such as background, brand logos, licence-plate data, and colour.

At a practical level, in this study, users are asked to order these profiles ranging from those that they consider the most typical of an electric car to those that they consider the least typical of an electric car. To this end, they are provided with 49 physical cards with printed photographs of the vehicles.

2.2.6 Data collection

Each respondent is given the 49 cards and asked to place them on a table in the order ranging from the most typical front of an electric car to those that they consider the least typical of an electric car based on their preference. Each user has unlimited time to carry out the experiment, with the average experiment time being approximately 7 minutes. Once the cards were sorted, the

established order was photographed, thereby enabling the researcher to record the profile numbers in the order given by each respondent.

2.2.7 Estimate the importance of attributes and the utilities of attribute levels

The importance scores are normally represented as a percentage (%), thus expressing the weight that the attribute holds in the users' preference, and thereby allowing one attribute to be compared with another.

In addition to this data from a conjoint analysis, information has also been collected regarding which profiles have been located most frequently in the first three positions (cars classified as the most electric) and the profiles most preferably located in the last three positions (cars classified as the least electric) (Dagher, Petiot, & Guyon, 2008; van der Lans & Heiser, 1992).

$$\hat{y}_i = \mu \sum_{j=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^{k_j} u_{jk} \times d_i(jk) \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the preference for profile i ; p is the number of attributes; k_j is the number of levels of attribute j ; u_{jk} is the utility for the level k of the attribute j ; $d_i(jk)$ is a dummy variable for the level k of the attribute j in the profile i ; μ is a constant of the model. The dummy variable of the model is a dichotomous variable that takes the value 1 when level k of attribute j is present in the profile and 0 otherwise. This variable defines the profile numerically in the model since the attributes under study are qualitative.

Once the utility scores have been obtained, the next step is to calculate the importance scores (Equation 2), which describe the impact (I_j) of the attributes on the preferences established by users (Dagher et al., 2008; Steiner & Meißner, 2018):

$$I_j = \frac{\max(u_{jk}) - \min(u_{jk})}{\sum_{i=1}^p \max(u_{ik}) - \min(u_{ik})} \quad (2)$$

The importance scores are normally represented as a percentage (%), thus expressing the weight that the attribute holds in the users' preference, thereby allowing one attribute to be compared with another.

In addition to this data from a conjoint analysis, information has also been collected on which profiles have been located most frequently in the first three positions (cars classified as most electric) and the profiles most preferably located in the last three positions (cars classified as less electric).

2.2.8 Evaluation of the validity

In order to analyse the predictive validity of the conjoint analysis, Pearson's R and Kendall's tau coefficient indicators are used. Specifically, Pearson's R measures the degree of correlation between attribute levels, and Kendall's tau measures the correlation between observed and estimated preferences. (Egeten, Prabowo, Gaol, & Meyliana, 2020; Oyatoye, Otike-obaro, & Nkeiruka, 2016). Each indicator has a hypothesis test through the p-value to analyse whether or not the user preference patterns differ from each other, thus analysing the internal consistency of the attribute levels.

2.3 Visual test

Once the 49 cards with images of the fronts of vehicles are delivered, users are asked whether they believed that the car represented on the card was an electric car or a combustion car. In this case, since these are images of real cars, the researchers have the correct answer for a posteriori comparison purposes in order to verify whether the respondents were correct or not, thus analysing the users' ability to recognise an electric car. The data collected in this test show the rate of success and failure of each user and also the overall rate. The visual test is helpful in achieving Objective 3 (O3), as defined above.

3. Results

To carry out the proposed methodology, 33 users of legal age from a university environment have participated by completing the three proposed tests (Figure 1): questionnaire survey or user test, the conjoint analysis, and the visual test.

3.1 Questionnaire survey

The sample of 33 users contains equal numbers regarding sex and age range. The results obtained from the questionnaire survey are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Participant characteristics (N=33)

Variables	Categories	n	%
P1: Sex	Woman	17	51.5
	Man	16	48.5
P2: Age	[18-21]	8	24.2
	[22-25]	9	27.3
	Over 25	16	48.5
P3: Driving licence	Yes	30	90.9
	In process	3	9.1
P4: Ecological choice	Yes	19	57.6
	No	14	42.4
P5: Purchase preference for a 100% electric vehicle	Price	6	18.2
	Autonomy	19	57.6
	Cargo volume	5	15.2
	Brand	1	3.0
	Power	2	6.1
P6: Desire to purchase a 100% electric vehicle	Yes	19	57.6
	No	14	42.4
P7: Ability to differentiate a 100% electric vehicle	Yes	7	21.2
	In doubt	17	51.5
	No	9	27.3

From the data provided in Table 1, it is worth highlighting that 57.6% of the preference in the purchase of an electric car is that of autonomy, rendering it the most important characteristic, which coincides with the studies analysed in Section 1. On the other hand, only 21.2% of those

surveyed believe they have the ability to recognise an electric car based solely on visual information.

The data obtained from the questionnaire survey or user test is utilised to segment the sample and carry out individual analyses in categories of variables, such as comparing the importance of the attributes obtained in the conjoint analysis based on the variable *Sex* (P1), to analyse whether there are differences in preferences between men and women. Those categories that have a low response frequency are not analysed since they are not statistically significant.

3.2 Conjoint Analysis

To carry out the proposed conjoint analysis, the IBM SPSS Statistics v.26.0 software is used with the objective of estimating the importance of attributes, estimating the utilities of attribute levels, and evaluating the validity of the analysis.

The IBM SPSS Statistics software contains no graphical interface to apply conjoint analysis, and therefore in order to run the analysis, the command syntax for the “CONJOINT” command must be written in the syntax window and executed. To run the analysis, two independent database files are required: on the one hand, a database with the 49 profiles obtained from applying the orthogonal design (Section 2.2.4), and on the other hand, a database with the preferences of the 33 respondents that must contain the established order of the 49 profiles of each respondent (Section 2.2.6). To apply the analysis, the “FACTORS” sub-command syntax must be taken into account, which enables specification of the model that describes the relationship between attributes and classifications. In this case, the model has been defined as “DISCRETE” since the levels of the defined attributes are categorical, and no assumption is made regarding the relationship between attributes and the order of preference established by users. Once the syntax command is executed, the global data shown in Tables 2 and 3 is obtained.

Table 2. Importance and utility score

Attribute	Importance score	Level	Utility
	21.583	A1 Arc	-0.172

		A2 Double arc	3.101
A: Headlight		A3 Fine	-0.271
form		A4 Polygonal	-1.094
		A5 Rounded	-1.564
B: Headlight	7.802	B1 Yes	-1.405
separation		B2 No	1.405
		C1 Long thin	2.480
		C2 Organic	-0.022
C: Grille form	34.325	C3 Banner	-6.396
		C4 Polygonal	-4.715
		C5 Visual	1.58
		C6 No grille	7.073
		D1 Big mouth	-3.161
		D2 Integrated	0.403
D: Front form	16.290	D3 Smile	1.384
		D4 Type U	0.332
		D5 Type X	1.042
		E1 Arc	2.389
E: Bonnet form	11.394	E2 Straight	-1.655
		E3 Straight arc	-0.734
		F1 Line	0.224
F: Bonnet nerve	8.606	F2 Double line	-0.347
		F3 No nerve	0.123

Firstly, in Table 2, the importance scores have been obtained for each attribute, which provides a measure of the relative importance of the attribute with respect to the global preference obtained from the classification of the profiles by the respondents. The importance values are calculated for each respondent separately, with the results average for all respondents shown in Table 2

The attributes with the highest importance value are the main attributes on which users have based themselves to classify the profiles as electric cars. The results show that the grille form (C) has the greatest influence (34.3%) on the total preference, which means that the grille form is the main identifying attribute of an electric car. The headlight form (A) plays a major role (21.6%) in the identification of the electric car followed by the front form (D) (16.3%). It can be said that the attributes with low influence on the detection of an electric vehicle are the attributes referring to the bonnet (E and F). Lastly, headlight separation (B) is the least significant attribute in the detection of an electric car (7.8%).

If the importance scores are analysed from the Pareto perspective (Figure 3) then it can be established that there are 33.33% of the attributes (grille form and headlight form) that accumulate 55.91% of the influence in the detection of whether a car is electric or combustion (Baroroh, Amalia, & Lestari, 2019).

Figure 3. Pareto diagram for the attributes of the front of an electric car

Table 2 also shows the utility score (partial contributions) of each attribute level. In this case, the higher the utility score, the greater the preference for that level in the definition of an electric car. Positive utility scores indicate relevant attribute levels in an electric car and negative utility scores are relevant attribute levels in combustion cars. To facilitate the analysis and comparison of the utility scores, these are represented graphically in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of estimated utility scores.

From Table 2 and Figure 4, it can be observed that the greatest influence on detecting a vehicle as being electric is the absence of a grille with a value of 7.07. The fact that a car either does not have a grille or does not have a clearly identifiable grille enables users to recognise it as an electric car. In contrast, banner grilles are the least characteristic of an electric car, and are therefore more typical of a combustion car. The second greatest influence in the classification is the headlight form type “double arc” with a utility value of 3.10, this being the only headlight form with a positive utility value. It should be noted that there is a difference of more than double the utility value between the “no grille” level and the headlight form type “double arc”, which accentuates the “no grille” as an identity characteristic of an electric car. Regarding the front form, the “smile” (1.38) and “type x” (1.04) levels are the greatest identifiers of an electric car, and both these front forms have close utility values.

Regarding the bonnet form, the “arc” type shape is the only form that obtains positive utility values (2.39), and therefore the bonnet form is the characteristic most associated with an electric car. Regarding the bonnet nerve, the utility scores are very close to 0, which indicates that the

levels have not been significant in the classification of the users. This is probably due to the nerve being the most subtle characteristic to appreciate in the graphic representation of the fronts of cars. Lastly, regarding the headlight separation, despite its position as the least important attribute, the fact of having non-separated headlights has been estimated as a characteristic level of an electric car with a utility score of 1.4.

With all the utility values expressed in a common unit and the constant value obtained (26.492) it is possible to establish the equation to calculate the total utility of any combination of levels based on Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{y}_i = & 26,492 - 0,172 \times d_{11} + 3,101 \times d_{12} - 0,271 \times d_{13} - 1,094 \times d_{14} - 1,564 \times d_{15} - 1,405 \times d_{21} \\ & + 1,405 \times d_{22} + 2,48 \times d_{31} - 0,022 \times d_{32} - 6,396 \times d_{33} - 4,715 \times d_{34} \\ & + 1,58 \times d_{35} + 7,073 \times d_{36} - 3,161 \times d_{41} + 0,403 \times d_{42} + 1,384 \times d_{43} \\ & + 0,332 \times d_{44} + 1,042 \times d_{45} + 2,389 \times d_{51} - 1,655 \times d_{52} - 0,734 \times d_{53} \\ & + 0,224 \times d_{61} - 0,347 \times d_{62} + 0,123 \times d_{63} \end{aligned}$$

Lastly, the conjoint analysis carried out in IBM SPSS Statistics evaluates the validity of the analysis carried out using Pearson's R and the Kendall's tau (Table 3).

Table 3. Correlations

Coefficient	Value	Sig.
Pearson's R	0.802	0.000
Kendall's tau	0.729	0.000

From the values obtained (Table 3), it can be observed that there is a correlation between the attribute levels of 0.802, and another correlation between the observed and estimated preferences of 0.729: it can therefore be concluded that these are satisfactory results for the study. The p-values (Sig. in Table 3) are employed to analyse the internal consistency of the attribute levels. Based on the data obtained, both p-values are less than 0.05 (95% confidence level), and hence it

can be established that the estimated opinion patterns of users do not differ much (Egeten et al., 2020).

Once the global results of the conjoint analysis for the 33 respondents have been analysed, a series of conjoint analyses are carried out for each of the categories of the variables of the questionnaire survey or user test (Table 1). These conjoint analyses aim to detect differences in preferences according to the 7 variables analysed in the user test. In this case, no details are given here regarding the 16 conjoint analyses carried out since the procedure is similar to that described above. A general overview is provided however, together with comments on those cases whose differences are significant.

Firstly, the most influential attributes in the recognition of electric cars are analysed, with the grille form being the most important attribute in the 16 groups analysed with an importance score greater than 31% in all groups (Figure 5). The second most influential attribute is the headlight form. This has an importance score greater than 20% in all groups except for users whose primary preference for the purchase of an electric vehicle is that of price. For this group of users, the front form (18.7%) has exerted a little more influence than the headlight form (18.6%). The front form is consolidated as the third most influential attribute for all groups, except for the group mentioned above. Lastly, it is worth highlighting a significant change in trend in users who responded “yes” to having the ability to differentiate a 100% electric vehicle. For these users, the fourth most influential attribute is headlight separation, with an importance value of 13.7%, whereby the average for the rest of the groups stands at 7.4%.

Figure 5. Graphical representation of the importance score (% , Y-axis) based on the categories of the user test variables (X-axis).

Regarding the analysis of the utility scores (Figure 6), a very similar trend is seen in the 16 groups analysed. It can be seen that the “no grille” level remains the most preferred attribute level in defining the front of an electric car. Based on the *Sex* variable (P1), significant differences are only observed in the front form, since in woman the level with the highest utility score is for front form type. For the *age* variable (P2), it can be seen that “no grille” continues to be the most useful, but as age advances the utility score of “no grille” decreases. The utility score for ages 18 to 21 is 9.966 (the highest utility score for “no grille” of all groups), for ages 22 to 25 this value is 7.459, and for those over 25 years of age the value is 5.410. Regarding the variable *Ability to differentiate a 100% electric vehicle* (P7), it is of note that those users who answered “no” maintain the lowest utility scores in the “no grille” level (3.295). The “long thin” form of grille is the most useful (3.708) for this group.

Figure 6. Graphical representation of the utility scores (Y-axis) based on the categories of the user test variables (X-axis).

Based on the data obtained from the importance scores (Figure 5) and the utility scores (Figure 6), it can be observed that the 16 groups analysed in terms of the categories of the questionnaire present very similar attribute preferences and levels, thereby confirming that the hypothesis obtained in Kendall's test shows that the pattern of user preferences is similar.

3.3 Visual test

Once the 49 profiles were presented, the 33 users were asked to establish, for each profile, whether, based on their criteria, they were looking at an electric car or a combustion car. Table 4 compiles a summary of the visual test data.

Table 4. Summary of successes and failures according to users

	Mean	%	SD	Max	Min
Successes	33.70	68.77	4.07	40	22
Failures	15.30	31.23	4.08	27	9

All respondents, bar one, have a success rate greater than 50%. It can be assumed that, by using images of real vehicles, the respondents were more familiar with said models and it was therefore easier to identify the cars correctly (Table 4).

Table 5. Summary of hits according to the vehicle propulsion system

Vehicle propulsion system	n	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
Electric	24	21.00	8.612	3	31
Combustion	25	24.32	6.095	11	33
Total	49	22.69	7.545	3	33

After having performed an analysis of variance (ANOVA), we found that the number of correct answers and errors in the visual test is independent of the type of vehicle (electric or combustion). The average number of correct answers in fossil-fuelled vehicles is slightly higher than the average number of correct answers in electric vehicles (Table 5). It is notable that electric cars have a lower minimum number of correct answers (3) than combustion vehicles (11), which since certain respondents found it difficult to guess correctly when it was an electric car.

Further to this general analysis, a series of ANOVAs have been carried out for the successes and failures based on the 7 variables of the user test (Table 1). From the ANOVAs carried out, it is obtained that the number of correct answers presents significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the variable *Ability to differentiate a 100% electric vehicle (P7)*. The average number of correct answers is significantly higher for respondents who answered that they are able to recognise an electric vehicle. This is the only variable (P7) that has a significant relationship with the number of correct answers, which is an indicator that users have answered honestly based on their recognition ability.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the attributes and levels of the front of electric and combustion cars helped establish, from the point of view of the respondents, that there are a series of characteristics that

today are associated with both electric and combustion cars. The detection and enhancement of these attributes and their levels would help generate a product identity based on the genuine characteristics of electric cars, which in turn may promote the use of these vehicles. To generate a product identity, it is essential to look for those attributes that make the electric car recognisable from other types of car and to this end this research has been carried out.

It can be stated that Hypothesis 1 (H1) of the study has been verified through Objective 1 (O1) and Objective 2 (O2), thereby reaching the following conclusion. An electric vehicle must contain the following attribute levels for the design of its front: grille form “no grille”; headlight form “double arc”; front form type “smile”; bonnet form “arc”; bonnet nerve “line”; and with no headlight separation. With these attribute levels, maximum utility is achieved according to Equation 1, and a utility value of 42.062 is obtained. There are two attributes whose levels barely differ from each other: front form and bonnet nerve. If, instead of using a front form type “smile”, a front form type “X” were used, then the total utility value would be 41.72. And if instead of using a bonnet nerve type “line”, a bonnet without nerve were used, then the total utility value would be 41.961.

Subsequent to the analysis, it can be stated that the grille is the most important identifying element on the front of an electric car, which is why it is suggested to design electric cars without a grille since they are not functionally necessary and are solely an inheritance from combustion vehicles (Koo, 2018). On the other hand, the headlight form type “double arc” is the most identifiable with electric vehicles, possibly because this type of headlight is technologically the most innovative and users tend to identify an electric car with the latest technological trends on the market.

Regarding Hypothesis 2 (H2), analysed through Objective 3 (O3), it can be stated that it is more difficult to identify an electric car than a combustion car, although in general no significant differences have been detected in the successes and failures based on the propulsion system.

Regarding Hypothesis 3 (H3), analysed through Objective 4 (O4), it cannot be stated that there are differences in the results based on demographic and social characteristics, such as sex, age,

and purchase intention, beyond that analysed in the Results section. It can be stated that the users who claim to be able to differentiate an electric car (21.2% of those surveyed) have presented significant differences in the rate of successes and failures and in the importance score.

With this type of study, we intend to continue in our investigation into the identity of a product such as the electric car and to serve as an aid to future formal aesthetic developments of electric cars. This type of study can be extended to other views of vehicles, such as the profile of the car or its rear, from which angle it can be significantly more difficult to differentiate between electric and combustion cars.

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